

A Study on Women Welfare Programmes in India

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: February

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Priyalatha, C. "A Study on Women Welfare Programmes in India." *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2019, pp. 91–94.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2551360>

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Abstract

Women play significant role in our society. Even after playing her all the roles and all the job timely in efficient manner in the modern society. she is weak because men are still strongest gender of the society. Even after lots of awareness programmes. Rules and regulations in the society by the government. Her life is more complicated than a man. She has to take care of herself and family members as daughter, sister, daughter –in- law, wife, mother, mother-in-law, grandmother, etc. The constitution of India allows a positive discrimination in favour of women. The article, under right to equality states; Nothing in this article shall prevent the state from making any special provision for women and children. So for the welfare of women, many programmes is implemented by Government, MINISTRY OF WOMEN AND CHILD DEVELOPMENT, Government of India have come up with various schemes, programmes social welfare schemes ,health and nutrition, scholarship for women. The schemes provides assistance for education, training, financial assistance, subsidy on the loans, scholarship, self employment and other facilities. The prime goal is for empowerment, development, protection and welfare of women and children. The necessary information about the programmes and its components are collected from books, journals, internet source.

Keywords: women welfare, programmes, policy, schemes, ministry of women and child development.

Introduction

Women are given first priority in India however on the other hand they were badly treated in the family and in society. They were limited only for the household chores or understand the responsibility of home and family members. They were kept totally unaware of their rights and own development. People of India say that our country ae Bharat-Mata, never realized the meaning of it. Women empowerment is very necessary. It is empowering women to understand their rights to be independent in every area for their proper growth and development. For this Government of India initiated so many programmes for women welfare. Welfare of women is a step towards all round development.

National Policy for Empowerment of Women

- In 2001, policy was formulated as the blueprint for the future, with the express of bringing about the advancement, development and empowerment of women.

- It laid down detailed prescription to address discrimination against women, strengthen legal systems, provide better health care access, equal opportunities for women's participation in decision making and mainstreaming gender concerns in development process.

Indira Gandhi Matritva Sahyog Yojana

- it is a conditional maternity benefit scheme.
- Cash incentive up from 4 k to 6 k to pregnant and lactating mothers aiming partly compensate them for wage loss during childbirth and childcare and also provide conditions for ensuring safe delivery and promote good nutrition and feeding practices for infants and young children.
- Central Sponsored Scheme under which financial assistance is provided as grant-in-aid to the state Government.
- Introduced in 2010 under the Ministry of Women and Child Development.
- All pregnant women of 19 years of age and above are eligible for the benefits under the scheme for the first two live births.
- The anganwadi workers play a vital role in identifying the beneficiaries to receive incentives under the scheme.

National Mission for Empowerment For Women

National Mission for Empowerment of women is an initiative of the Government of India for empowering Women holistically. It is conceived as an umbrella mission with a mandate to strengthen inter-sectoral convergence and facilitate the process of coordinating all the women's welfare and socio economic development programme across ministries and departments.

The Salient Features of the Programme are

- To ensure economic empowerment of women.
- To ensure that violence against women is eliminated.
- To ensure social empowerment of women with emphasis on health and education.
- To undertake awareness generation as well as activities to demand for benefits under various schemes and programmes.
- To oversee gender mainstreaming of programmes, policies, institutional arrangement, and processes of participating Ministries, Institutions and Organizations.

PSK (POORNA SHAKTHI KENDRA) Under NMEW as one stop service centre to women at District and Gram panchayat level.

- A model intervention project under NMEW established in villages, for offering services to women at the grassroots.
- Working with the motto, HUM SUNENGE NARI KI BAAT (we will listen to women's voices)
- Two women coordinators or Gram samanvayaks in each Kendra.
- One of the important elements of the project is to stress on processes instrumental in bringing about women's empowerment through convergence strategies on the ground.

Functions of PSK

- To reach out the information to women about all the government programmes, services, schemes and helping them to utilize the benefits providing by the Government. Further, to facilitate to avail those benefits especially related to health, education, and, livelihood.
- To conduct capacity building training programme to women on various issues like leadership qualities, crisis management, stress management, life skills development, legal rights and entitlements etc in order to create awareness and enhancing their knowledge and skills.

- To maintain a database of target population on various issues related to women.
- To coordinate with the outreach services of various departments.
- To organize women into clusters to access various services and to strengthen SHGs.

Step (Support to Training and Employment Programme)

- Central sector scheme launched in 1986-87.
- Enabling women to take up employment cum income generation programmes.

Seeks to upgrade skills of poor and asset less women and provide employment on sustainable basis by mobilizing them in viable cooperative groups, strengthening marketing linkages, support services and access to credit. The ultimate endeavour of each project is to develop the group to thrive on a self-sustaining basis in the group to thrive on a self-sustaining basis in the market place with minimal governmental support and intervention even after the project period is over.

RMK (Rashtriya Mahila Kosh)

Rmk or National credit fund for women was set up in in 1993. Since its registration, Rmk has established itself as the premier micro- credit agency of the country, with its focus on women and their empowerment through the provision of credit for livelihood related activities.

Aim

The aim is to make Rmks to alleviate poverty through credit support to the female members for income generation, skill upgradation.

Women Empowerment and Livelihood Programme in Mid ---- Gangetic plains (Priyadarshini)

From the year 2011, the Ministry is administering IFAD assisted pilot project namely Women Empowerment and Livelihoods programme in 13 blocks spread over five districts in uttar Pradesh and two districts in Bihar. The programme aims at holistic empowerment (econ mic and social) of vulnerable groups of women and adolescent girls in the project area through formation of women self Help Groups and promotion of improved livelihood opportunities. Over 1,00,000 households are to be covered under the project and 7,200 SHGs will be formed during the project period. Swadhar(scheme for women in Difficult Circumstances)

Swadhar was launched by the Ministry during the year 2001-02 for the benefit of women in difficult circumstances with the following objectives.

- To provide primary need of shelter , food ,clothing and care to be the marginalized women ,girls living in difficult circumstances who are without any social and economic support.
- To provide emotional support and counseling to rehabilitate them socially and economically.
- To arrange for specific clinical, legal, and other support for women in need and.
- To provide for help line or other facilities to such women in distress.

Scheme for Combating Trafficking

“Ujjawala”, a comprehensive scheme to combat trafficking was launched by the Ministry in the year 2007 and is being implemented mainly through NGOs. The scheme has five components – Prevention, Rescue, Rehabilitation, Re –Integration and Repatriation of trafficked victims for commercial sexual exploitation.

Conclusion

Women are powerful and beautiful entity of the world. Women leadership is restricted by the various social, cultural, and political norms which need to be addressed. First of all we need to address all the social inequalities hindering women advancement in order to change women

situation in the society as well as nation. Women role in society is highly appreciable so women welfare is important. The Government of India initiated so many programmes, policies, schemes for welfare of women.

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